

VENOUS ULCERS: A CLINICAL REVIEW**Dr. Rina Gupta*¹, Dr. Ranjit Singh², Dr. Bhoomi Soni³**PG Scholar¹, Professor², Associate Professor³

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ABSTRACT

Venous ulcers, also known as stasis or varicose ulcers, represent the most common form of chronic lower limb ulcers and are a major public health concern worldwide. They are primarily caused by a chronic venous insufficiency resulting in venous hypertension and subsequent tissue breakdown. This review highlights the etiology, clinical presentation, diagnostic approaches and current evidence-based management strategies for venous ulcers, while emphasizing the importance of preventive measures and long-term care. Chronic Venous insufficiency(CVI) is a long standing disorder of the venous system in which venous valve incompetence and/or obstruction leads to venous hypertension, impaired venous return, and a cascade of microcirculatory changes.^[1]

KEYWORDS: Venous ulcer, chronic venous insufficiency, compression therapy, stasis ulcer, wound management.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic wounds impose a substantial socioeconomic and healthcare burden globally with venous ulcers accounting for approximate 70-80% of leg ulcers in developed nations.^[2] These ulcers typically develop around the gaiter area of leg (especially near the medial malleolus) and are associated with symptoms such as varicose vein, edema, skin pigmentation, and eczema.^[1] They are typically recurrent, slow healing, and significantly impact patient quality of life by limiting mobility and increasing the risk of infection. Despite advances in wound care, recurrence rates remain high without comprehensive management of the underlying venous pathology. The underlying cause is chronic venous insufficiency (CVI), in which damage to the

venous valves leads to venous hypertension, capillary leakage and tissue hypoxia. These pathophysiological changes impair wound healing and predispose to ulcer formation.^[3]

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The pathogenesis of venous ulcers is primarily related to chronic venous insufficiency. Incompetent venous valves and / or venous obstruction lead to venous hypertension. This results in^[4]

- Increased capillary hydrostatic pressure.
- Leakage of plasma proteins and red blood cells into the interstitial tissue.
- Pericapillary fibrin deposition, leukocyte trapping, and chronic inflammation.
- Tissue hypoxia and eventual skin breakdown.
- Failure of the calf muscle pump.
- Obstruction to venous flow following deep vein thrombosis or trauma.

The “fibrin cuff hypothesis” and “leukocytes trapping hypothesis” are widely accepted mechanisms explaining under development.

RISK FACTORS

Several predisposing factors increases the likelihood of venous ulcer formation, including:

- History of varicose veins or deep vein thrombosis [DVT]
- Obesity and sedentary lifestyle
- Older age
- Previous leg trauma or surgery
- Occupations requiring prolonged standing
- Family history of venous disease

CLINICAL PRESENTATION

Venous ulcers typically occur in the gaiter region of the leg, most commonly around the medial malleolus.

Key clinical features include

- Ulcer with shallow depth and irregular margins.
- Exudative wound base, often covered with granulation tissue.
- Surrounding skin changes: hemosiderin deposition, lipodermatosclerosis, venous eczema, and atrophie blanche.

- Mild to moderate pain, worsened by dependency and relieved by leg elevation.
- Associated limb edema and varicose veins.

DIAGNOSTIC EVALUATION

Diagnosis is largely clinical but supported by vascular investigations.

- **DUPLEX DOPPLER ULTRASOUND:** Gold standard for assessing venous reflux and obstruction
- **ANKLE- BRACHIAL PRESSURE INDEX [ABPI]:**
Essential to exclude coexisting arterial disease before initiating compression therapy [ABPI<0.8 suggests significant arterial disease]
- **LABORATORY TESTS:** Limited role; may be used to rule out infection or systemic disease

MANAGEMENT

GENERAL PRINCIPLES

The goals of management are to promote ulcer healing, alleviate symptoms, prevent recurrence, and improve quality of life.

1. WOUND CARE

- Regular cleansing with non-irritating solutions
- Moist wound dressings tailored to exudate level
- Avoidance of cytotoxic antiseptics

2. COMPRESSION THERAPY

- Cornerstone of venous ulcer treatment
- Multilayer elastic bandages or compression stocking (30-40mmHg)
- Enhance venous return, reduces edema, and accelerate healing

3. PHARMACOTHERAPY

- Venoactive agents such as micronized purified flavonoid fraction (MPFF)
- Pentoxifylline as an adjunct to compression therapy
- Antibiotics reserved for clinically infected ulcers

4. LIFESTYLE MODIFICATION

- Leg elevation and regular walking to enhance calf muscle pump function
- Weight reduction and smoking cessation

5. SURGICAL AND ENDOVASCULAR INTERVENTIONS

- Endovenous ablation (laser or radiofrequency)
- Sclerotherapy for varicosities
- Vein stripping in selected cases
- Skin grafting for non-healing ulcers

COMPLICATIONS^[5]

If untreated, venous ulcer may progress to

- Recurrent cellulites and secondary bacterial infection
- Osteomyelites in chronic cases
- Malignant transformation (Marjolin's ulcer, though rare)
- Chronic pain and reduced mobility
- Deep vein thrombosis(DVT)
- Periostitis
- Haemorrhage
- Talipes equino-varus deformity

PROGNOSIS

The healing of venous ulcers may take weeks to months, with recurrence rates reported as high as 70% within five years if underlying venous hypertension is not addressed. Lifelong compression therapy and regular follow -up are critical for reducing recurrence.

CONCLUSION

Venous ulcers remain a common and challenging clinical condition with significant implications for patient well-being and healthcare systems.

Optimal management requires a **multidisciplinary approach**, combining effective wound care, compression therapy, lifestyle modification, and where indicated, surgical correction of venous pathology. Early diagnosis, patient education, and adherence to preventive strategies are essential to reduce recurrence and improve long-term outcomes.

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